

From the study of the effect of temperature on reaction rate, energy of activation and entropy of activation have been found to be 12.56 kcal mol⁻¹ and -38.65 e.u. with salicylidene *o*-aminophenol and 12.60 kcal mol⁻¹ and -38.70 e.u. with salicylidene *m*-aminophenol as substrate. The following mechanism explain all the kinetic results :

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Quenching of 3-Methyl-5-phenylpyrazole Cation Fluorescence by Inorganic Anions

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INORGANIC anions have been found to be effective in quenching the fluorescence of many organic compounds and a donor-acceptor interaction has been proposed as the most likely mechanism of quenching¹. These halide ions quench the fluorescence of electron acceptors by acting as donor either in the formation of ground state charge transfer complex² or in the formation of excited state charge transfer complex³⁻⁵. In continuation of our earlier work^{6,7} on pyrazoles and substituted pyrazoles, we have now examined the fluorescence quenching of 3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazole (MPP) cation by halide and thiocyanate anions.

Experimental

3-Methyl-5-phenylpyrazole was prepared from benzoylacetone and hydrazine hydrate⁸ and purified by repeated recrystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether mixture. The purity of the compound was tested by its constant emission maxima with different

excitation wavelengths. The cation of MPP was produced by the addition of concentrated H₂SO₄. Water used was deionised and distilled from alkaline KMnO₄, and deaerated by passing oxygen-free nitrogen. Potassium chloride, potassium bromide, potassium iodide, potassium thiocyanate (all AnalaR) were used as such. Absorption spectra were recorded with a JASCO UNIDEC-650 spectrophotometer and fluorescence measurements were made with a JASCO FP-550 spectrofluorimeter. Experimental solutions were prepared using concentrated H₂SO₄, potassium sulphate and the quencher ion solution. Sulphuric acid and potassium sulphate as ionic buffer were used because it was found that sulphate ion did not quench the fluorescence⁶. Fixed aliquot of stock solution of MPP in methanol (spectrograde) was added to each experimental solution and the resulting concentration of MPP cation was about 10⁻⁵ M. There was no observable shift in wavelength of the fluorescence spectra of MPP cation upon the addition of quenchers. All fluorescence measurements were made at 315 nm.

Results and Discussion

Quenching constants (K_{sv}) for chloride, bromide, iodide and thiocyanate ions were determined using Stern-Volmer relationship⁹ (1),

$$I_0/I - 1 = K_{sv}[Q] \quad (1)$$

where I_0 and I are fluorescence intensities (uncorrected) at a given wavelength in the absence and presence of a concentration $[Q]$ of the quencher respectively. The plot of I_0/I vs concentration of quencher was perfectly linear in all the cases. The average of K_{sv} values obtained from equation (1) and graphical K_{sv} values agreed well. Table 1 shows the quenching constants for the inorganic anions with their redox potentials¹⁰. The linearity of Stern-Volmer plot shows that only one quenching mechanism is operative¹¹ for the quenching by all anions. There was no change in the absorption spectrum of MPP cation with different concentrations of quencher ion (within the limit of the concentration of the quencher used) when compared with the absorption spectra taken without quencher. This rules out the quenching by ground state complex formation, i.e. static quenching.

In the absence of ground state complex formation, quenching must be either by the charge transfer complex formation in the excited state^{4,12} or by the external heavy atom effect which induces intersystem crossing^{13,14}. If these anions derived their quenching ability from external heavy-atom spin-orbit coupling then the quenching constant might be expected to depend on the square of the atomic spin-orbit coupling parameter¹³ of the heavy atom. This leads to the following predicted order of quenching, I⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻ > CNS⁻. The observed order of quenching (Table 1) is I⁻ > CNS⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻. This order is different from the spin-orbit coupling parameter but it is the order of redox potentials. Hence

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quenching may be considered to occur by the formation of excited state charge transfer complex (exciplex),

where ${}^1A^+$ is MPP cation in the S_1 state, X^- the anion, and ${}^1(A^+ \cdot X^-)$ the exciplex.

Soloman *et al.*¹⁵ developed a treatment for the process of exciplex formation by electron transfer. Accordingly the energy of the electron transfer step (2) is given by equation (3),

$$\Delta F \approx {}^1\Delta E_A + IP_D - EA_A - C \quad (3)$$

where, ${}^1\Delta E_A$ is the singlet excitation energy of the acceptor, IP_D the ionisation energy of the donor anion, EA_A the electron affinity of the acceptor and C is a term for coulombic energy on forming the complex, in its equilibrium configuration, from the components. This expression refers to the gas phase and in solution there will be an additional term for the difference in free energies of solvation of ${}^1(A^+ \cdot X^-)$ and ${}^1A^+$ and X^- . For the same acceptor and same solvent and assuming constancy for the term C , the equation (3) becomes

$$\Delta F \approx \text{Constant} + IP_D \quad (4)$$

The equation (4) predicts a linear correlation between $\log K_{sv}$ and IP_D . The ionisation potentials of the anions are related to the redox potentials for $2X^- \rightleftharpoons X_2 + 2e$. So if this mechanism is operative, $\log K_{sv}$ values should have a linear correlation with redox potentials of the anions. A good linear correlation (correlation coefficient = 0.9935) is obtained from the data of Table 1. From the straight line plot of $\log K_{sv}$ vs redox potentials of anions (not shown), the

TABLE 1—QUENCHING CONSTANTS (K_{sv}) AND $\log K_{sv}$ VALUES FOR QUENCHING 3-METHYL-5-PHENYL-PYRAZOLE CATION FLUORESCENCE BY A RANGE OF ANIONS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS

Quencher	K_{sv} dm ³ mol ⁻¹	$\log K_{sv}$	Redox potential* (V)
Cl ⁻	23.00	1.3617	1.36
Br ⁻	57.89	2.7626	1.07
CNS ⁻	333.00	2.5223	0.77
I ⁻	800.00	2.9031	0.54

*From Ref. 10.

slope is found to be -1.9530. A large and negative value of the slope reveals that quenching is more sensitive to redox potential of the anion and also lower the value of the potential, the higher the quenching efficiency. This again confirms the charge transfer mechanism. Based on the correlation of quenching constant (K_{sv}) with redox potential this mechanism was proposed for quenching by inorganic anions by several authors^{2,10,16}.

All solutions were tested for the emission at longer wavelength. Since no emission was observed, the exciplex is non-fluorescent in all cases. In conclusion, the data obtained indicate that the anion-induced

quenching of the fluorescence of MPP cation proceeds through charge transfer mechanism. The following scheme is proposed for the interaction of the MPP cation with the electron donor anion,

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